

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

IN THE KING COUNTY SUPERIOR COURT
STATE OF WASHINGTON

STATE OF WASHINGTON,

Plaintiff,

vs.

ANTHONY WAYNE JONES,

Defendant.

No. 24-1-00375-1 SEA

MOTION FOR PRE-TERMINATION
CLARIFICATION OF LEGAL
AUTHORITY AND FRAMEWORK
TO ENSURE PROCEDURAL
FAIRNESS

ORAL ARGUMENT REQUESTED

I. RELIEF SOUGHT

COMES NOW Defendant Anthony Wayne Jones (“Defendant”), by and through his attorney of record, Francis G. Huguenin of Carson Law Group, PLLC, and respectfully moves this Court pursuant to its inherent authority and Defendant’s Constitutional right to procedural Due Process, for an Order clarifying and specifying

MOTION FOR PRE-TERMINATION CLARIFICATION
OF LEGAL AUTHORITY AND FRAMEWORK TO
ENSURE PROCEDURAL FAIRNESS - 1

CARSON LAW GROUP, PLLC
3113 ROCKEFELLER AVE
EVERETT, WASHINGTON 98201
(425) 493-5000 • (425) 493-5004 (FAX)

1 on the record the precise jurisdictional legal authority under which it imposes
2 Sanctions, Exclusion Orders, and adjudicates Termination.

3 In doing so, Defendant further respectfully requests that this Court make
4 findings as to whether Drug Court Proceedings are governed by criminal law
5 principles, administrative law principles, contract law principles, or some hybrid
6 framework. Should the latter apply, it is also critical for the Court to identify which
7 aspects are governed by which legal regime.
8

9 When considering Defendant's request, this Court can take judicial notice that
10 there appears to be no applicable Washington State precedent addressing this core
11 jurisdictional issue, making this a matter of first impression.

12 II. STATEMENT OF FACTS

13 1. April 15, 2025 Hearing (Authority Asked; Answer Unclear; Invitation to Brief):

14 At the April 15, 2025, Status Hearing, Defendant (then *pro se*) asked the Court
15 on the record to identify the legal source and regime of sanctioning power and
16 whether Sanctions were grounded in contract. *Subjoined Declaration of*
17 *Anthony Wayne Jones*, ¶ 3 and Exhibit 1 herein. The Court stated, in
18 substance, that this is “*a criminal proceeding ... not a contract proceeding*,”
19 while simultaneously invoking Waiver/Handbook provisions, including ¶ 13 of
20 the Waiver and Agreement at the end of Drug Court's Policy and Procedure
21 Manual, as operative authority for Sanctions. *Id.* The Court expressly invited
22 motion practice on the issue by conveying to Defendant that he “*would need to*
23
24

1 P.3d 972 (2014). If the State insists the regime is criminal to justify
2 punishment, it must concede criminal-procedure protections, which are not
3 provided and have not been afforded to Defendant.

4 **B. Drug Court’s Authority is not Standalone Statutory.** RCW 2.30.030 authorizes
5 courts to establish therapeutic courts, such as this Drug Court. But it does not
6 define violations, set burdens, or prescribe procedures or remedies. At its core,
7 RCW 2.30.030 is an enabling statute.¹ Even if the State contends RCW
8 2.30.030 delegates sanction-setting, Washington’s nondelegation doctrine
9 requires either meaningful standards/guidelines or adequate procedural
10 safeguards; RCW 2.30.030 provides neither for punitive “program sanctions.”
11 See *Barry & Barry, Inc. v. Dep’t of Motor Vehicles*, 81 Wn.2d 155, 163–64, 500
12 P.2d 540 (1972) (two-part test: standards or safeguards); see also *Associated*
13 *Gen. Contractors of Wash. v. State*, 200 Wn.2d 396, 403-04, 518 P.3d 639 (2022)
14 (reaffirming *Barry & Barry* two-part framework). Delegating ad hoc power to
15 impose punitive consequences without standards risks the exact unfettered
16 discretion *Barry* forbids; at minimum, sanctions cannot rest on RCW 2.30.030
17 unless explicit standards are adopted and stated on the record. *State v. Crown*

18
19
20
21
22 ¹ Persuasive authority exists from other jurisdictions. See *Diaz v. State*, 884 So. 2d 299 (Fla. 2d DCA 2004) (no
23 statutory authority for jailing a pre-plea drug-court participant based on a “Drug Court Agreement”); *Mullin v.*
24 *Jenne*, 890 So. 2d 543 (Fla. 4th DCA 2005) (reaching the opposite result under then-existing Broward PTI order);
25 and *Walker v. Lamberti*, 29 So. 3d 1172, 1173–74 (Fla. 4th DCA 2010) (explaining that, after *Diaz* and *Mullin*, the
26 Legislature amended the law to “expressly provide that incarceration or placement in jail-based drug programs may
27 be imposed as a sanction,” citing Ch. 2006-97, § 8, Laws of Fla., and Fla. Stat. § 948.08(6)(b); also citing §
28 397.334(5) requiring a written, coordinated sanctions strategy).

1 *Zellerbach Corp.*, 92 Wn.2d 894, 899–901, 602 P.2d 1172 (1979) (unlawful if an
2 agency can define offense/penalty with unrestricted discretion; “If an
3 administrative agency may in its sole and unrestricted discretion define the
4 crime or impose the penalty, there is an unlawful delegation”). *Id.* at 901.

5
6 **C. Drug Court’s Authority is not “Inherent” as a Substitute Code.** Inherent power
7 is narrow (housekeeping, order) and cannot create a free-floating program
8 penalty scheme; punitive consequences must track statutory contempt or
9 another defined source. *State v. Browet, Inc.*, 103 Wn.2d 215, 218–19, 691 P.2d
10 571 (1984).

11 **D. Field Guidance Frames the Waiver and Agreement as a Contract.** All Rise,
12 Drug Court’s Best Practices Publisher, hosts the Adult Drug Court Planning
13 Initiative’s (“ADCPI”) *A Guide to Creating a Participant Handbook*, which
14 instructs that “the final page of the handbook should be the participant
15 contractual agreement,” signed by the Participant and witnessed by Program
16 Staff, with the original retained in the participant’s file. *Subj. Jones*
17 *Declaration*, ¶ 4 and Exhibit 2, ¶ 24 herein. Identically the Court and State for
18 King County Drug Court have relied on Waiver and Agreement terms as
19 operative authority, requiring the same placement and indicia of
20 authentication as is recommended by ADCPI. *Statement of Facts*, ¶ 1; *Exhibits*
21 *to Mason Declaration in Support of State’s Petition to Terminate*, Ex. 2, p. 60,
22
23
24

¶ 13. Fundamentally, that is contract enforcement. Washington contract law therefore governs.

2. Issue No. 2: Due Process Requires the Governing Regime and Standards Be Identified Before Termination Proceeds

Washington decisions require clear notice of the rule/grounds, a meaningful opportunity to contest, and findings keyed to a defined standard in drug-court termination. *State v. Harrison*, 24 Wn. App. 2d 40, 48–51, 519 P.3d 244 (2022); *State v. Cassill-Skilton*, 122 Wn. App. 652, 656–61, 94 P.3d 407 (2004); *State v. Starkgraf*, 29 Wn. App. 2d 30, 45–47, 50, 539 P.3d 855 (2023), *review denied*, 2 Wn.3d 1032 (2024). Federal touchstones are the same – the process must be calibrated to minimize the risk of erroneous deprivation. *Mathews v. Eldridge*, 424 U.S. 319, 335 (1976).

Drug Courts may be distinct, *Sykes*, 182 Wn.2d at 175–78, but “distinct” does not mean lawless. The Court must choose and announce the governing doctrine and its standards/burdens before adjudicating Termination.

This sort of clarity is not academic; the governing doctrine dictates the defense itself. Without a declared source of authority, a participant cannot (i) know the elements or grounds to meet, (ii) identify the standard of proof or who bears the burden, (iii) determine which evidentiary and confrontation rules apply, (iv) select cognizable defenses, (v) seek the proper remedies (e.g., contract enforcement/record correction versus contempt purge conditions), or (vi) build the right record for review

1 at the appellate level. That is exactly why due process requires the rule and standard
2 to be stated before adjudication. *Mathews*, 424 U.S. at 335; *Harrison*, 24 Wn. App. 2d
3 at 48–51.

4 V. CONCLUSION

5 The April 15, 2025 Transcript (Exhibit 1 herein) demonstrates that this Court
6 has been unable to identify the specific legal authority governing its Sanctioning and
7 Termination powers. This uncertainty violates due process and frustrates meaningful
8 participation in proceedings.

9 Even with detailed factual allegations, notice without the governing authority
10 is illusory. A list of facts tells Mr. Jones what happened; it does not tell him whether
11 those facts amount to a violation under contract, contempt, or criminal procedure,
12 what elements the State must meet, what standard and burden apply, what defenses
13 are cognizable, or what remedies are available. Due process requires notice that
14 enables a meaningful response - rule plus standard - not just a narrative. Until such
15 time that this occurs, then the Notice requirement for Termination has arguably not
16 been satisfied.

17 With the above as foundation, Mr. Jones respectfully requests that this Court
18 grant the relief set forth above.

19 VI. PROPOSED ORDER

20 A proposed Order accompanies this Motion.

21
22
23
24
25 MOTION FOR PRE-TERMINATION CLARIFICATION
26 OF LEGAL AUTHORITY AND FRAMEWORK TO
27 ENSURE PROCEDURAL FAIRNESS - 7

CARSON LAW GROUP, PLLC
3113 ROCKEFELLER AVE
EVERETT, WASHINGTON 98201
(425) 493-5000 • (425) 493-5004 (FAX)

1 DATED this 13th day of August, 2025.

2 CARSON LAW GROUP, PLLC

3 */s/ Francis G. Huguenin*

4 _____
5 Francis G. Huguenin, WSBA #47098
6 Attorney for Defendant

7 I certify that this Memorandum contains 1,310 words, in compliance with the Local
8 Civil Rules.

Exhibit 1

Katrina Thornton: 044491, and 241003751, Seattle designation, I would like to memorialize what we..

Judge Mchale: we just lost Tony.

Katrina Thornton: I would like to memorialize what was discussed during staffing Your Honor, when we were all off the record. As mentioned, Tony is pro se representing himself in these matters. Before memorializing that conversation, I would ask the court to again request whether there is anyone reporting the hearing via zoom or in person.

Judge Mchale: Okay, per gr 16, usually when there is to be a recording or videography or photographs in court, someone is generally or is to ask or check in with the bailiff about that. Wanted to make sure that no one had requested to do that at this point, is there anyone here that's recording this proceeding, either the video of it or the audio? Our record is preserved here by our clerk, so we're on the record since we started the hearing, and that would be the official recording of this proceeding. So anyone who's present with us on Zoom?

Cynthia Herring: No, I'm not recording your honor.

Judge Mchale: Okay, thank you and for the record, who was that?

Cynthia Herring: Sorry. This is Cynthia. I'm also here with Brent Donner a lot.

Judge Mchale: Okay, thank you. All right.

Francis Huegenin: Good afternoon, Your Honor. This is Francis Huegenin, and no, I'm not recording.

Judge Mchale: okay.

Francis Huegenin: I'm here merely as an observer. Thank you.

Judge Mchale: Thank you. Okay, alright.

Katrina Thornton: We have one additional individual on Zoom, Erica Barnett. I would ask that she identify herself and confirm that she's not recording this proceedings.

Erica Barnett: Your Honor. Hi, it's Erica. I'm not recording.

Judge Mchale: okay. Thank you very much.

Katrina Thornton: So to put on the record what we discussed in staffing your honor. Your honor noted that you're aware of a motion Tony is intending to file it as noted, was not properly noted and served. It's not properly noted before this court originally, it was not properly served

on the prosecutor's office. I do acknowledge received via email, however, under the court rules, that is not a proper service unless otherwise agreed. Your Honor, inquired with Tony and indicated that it seems as if he does have some problems with the drug court program. And you asked if he wanted to keep at it and remain in the program. He indicated that he does want to remain in the program, and when he did opt into the program, he wasn't aware that there were quote, unquote testing errors and that his honest efforts could be invalidated. Your Honor, remind He also noted that when he opted in that he wasn't aware that quote, wrong testing was not able to be contested. Your Honor, reminded Tony that he does not represent other participants in this program, and reminded him to focus on himself and his own programming. Your Honor, discussed with Tony the the sanctions that had been imposed when he tested positive for xylazine, and discussed how specifically, the compliance clock does not amount to a loss of liberty, such that incarceration does and you differentiated between the two. Tony then indicated that he had not an incident at housing, but had Discussion with the housing case managers at the facility where he is residing. He claimed that his housing was threatened after he requested to have, I believe it was a copy of the contract that he initially signed when he moved into drug court housing. Your Honor, noted that that drug court and the housing provided by drug court are both an opportunity to address substance use disorder and gain legal benefits upon successful completion of the program. You specifically noted that drug court, the drug Diversion Court program, and the housing provided by this program are voluntary, and nobody is required to either be in the program or remain at drug court housing specifically, but I will just note I didn't mention this in staffing. I didn't think about it, but sometimes in transfer agreements, Your Honor, we'll see that one of the conditions that I include is reside at drug court approved housing. So just wanted to differentiate what we mean by by voluntary, that nobody is required to remain against this program, against their will. It's a privilege, not an obligation. I mean, there are obligations, but your honor knows what I'm saying. It's a voluntary program.

Judge Mchale: Before I go to Tony on this like the first thing that we talked about in the staffing is what's in the status report for today's hearing, and that indicates that Tony's in compliance with treatment, his sober supports and healthy social activities have been verified. His UAs are negative. Treatment reports that Tony attended all treatment activities as scheduled and as a strong participant in the program. Treatment reports that Tony's given some thought to vocational options on building connections with some of the other participants in the program. Treatment reports that Tony is nearly finished with his MRT step work and doing well in that group by regularly presenting and providing insights. Recommendation is that Tony is an express on phase three, where the next hearing request of May the sixth in the afternoon in person, so that's that's what we had to start you to clarify what took place in the staffing Tony. Is there anything that you want to add?

Anthony Jones: I just did want to present for the record that this morning I was threatened with removal from drug court housing by the wealth program director named Jody, not for any misconduct or violation, but for speaking about my legal case and raising constitutional concerns. The threat was explicit. Unless I stopped discussing my findings, court proceedings and policy critiques of this program, I'll lose my housing. Weld is a drug court contracted vendor funded by the county that makes this a statement threat tied directly to protected First

Amendment activity. I'm preserving this now to make clear that any subsequent housing action against me will be treated as retaliatory and included in my forthcoming 1983 federal filing.

Judge Mchale: Okay,

Anthony Jones: I'm not asking for relief. I'm preserving the record for future proceedings.

Judge Mchale: Okay? And again, all, all we're addressing here in this hearing are in your cases, the two under the cause numbers that are before the court, are state of Washington versus versus Tony or Anthony W Jones is listed in the waiver and agreements to come in. In the staffing, as Katrina stated, You know, there was some talk of my concern about whether you wanted to still stay in this program, because there have been emails that have been sent to the others that the court has been CC'd on, indicating that you have complaints with certain issues with the drug court program. So my understanding in our staffing, and I'll ask you now on the record is, is it your desire to stay here and complete the drug court program through Phase Five and to graduation.

Anthony Jones: Yes, Your Honor. As I, as I stated during the staffing that you know, when I opted in, I made promises to do, to do certain things, and that includes everything that's needed to graduate. I aim to honor my word.

Judge Mchale: And per the policy and procedure, manual and the handbook, the the program. It is a it's a voluntary program. It's an opportunity. It's an opportunity that people didn't have at the height of the the drug war. Wasn't until 1994 that we got started here. And there's a case that I think talks pretty well about why we're here. It addressed a different issue, but in dicta, it explains it pretty well. And the name of the case is state versus Sykes in That's at 182 Washington second 186 and it says adult drug courts are philosophically, functionally and intentionally different from ordinary courts. That goes down to say, ordinarily, an adult who is found guilty of criminal activity is subject to penalties that are intended to protect the public by deferring criminal conduct and incapacitating those who engage in it. In the case of certain adults who commit non violent offenses motivated by drug abuse or dependence, however, ordinary criminal penalties can be ineffective because they do not address the offenders underlying drug issues, leaving them highly likely to reach recent to recidivate after a brief period of in cap incapacitation at public expense adult drug courts or a judicial response to this problem and its enormous fiscal and societal costs. So it's just a it's a tremendous opportunity, as I see it, to give people a chance to change their lives. And it's voluntary. And when one comes into the program, they, as you did, knowingly, intelligently and voluntarily waive certain rights in signing an agreement that allows you to come into the program. You did that on November the 26th on both of your cause numbers with that, and paragraph 13 provides that you understand and agree that any violation of drug court requirements, such as a positive dilute or adulterated urinalysis test, missed treatment session, any failure to abide by the terms of the agreement or commission of a new crime may result in modification of the treatment program, imposition of a sanction, revocation of my conditional release and or termination from the program. And then paragraph 15 of that provides that you knowingly, freely and voluntarily

enter into the agreement. So the goal, the goal is to provide another way than just sending people to prison. It's to help people get control of their substance use issues. I mean, another goal, of course, is to ultimately have your case dismissed. But that's to me, that's kind of part and parcel of the new life that one gets in drug court. Because if you get in control of yourself with your substance use issue, your life has no bounds, and it's even less shackled by convictions that come with the cause numbers that bring people in. So the only way the program is successful is to have people who are successful in it. So I, I want you, I want every participant who's here, every participant that's in this program, to get control of their lives, to graduate, to get beyond this and to be successful and never have to go into criminal court again. That's the overall goal of it, and I just want to make sure that you understand that, and that you agreed to come in and comply with the terms of it, and that it's kind of where we are. On your part, a clear example of that is where you are and being in today's hearing, which is being an Express. You've done everything that you need to do to be an express here in phase three for today's hearing, it's, you know, it's different being a pro se person in the court, but I don't have a doubt that you can be compliant and ultimately, get get through the program successfully, but the focus needs to be on you, State of Washington versus Tony Jones, rather than on on other people or necessarily broader issues on the program that are not directly your issues. So that's, that's what I—I've gone on longer than I wanted to; but when I see the ongoing issues that you had with things it was apparent to me that, or at least it appeared to me that maybe you no longer wanted to voluntarily be here with us. So that's where I am coming in, I guess for today's hearing, solely for today's hearing, that's what we got going on, we had a talk in the staffing beforehand, and have been through this now here on the record, I'm as we do with all hearings as we do with an express, i commend you with doing that. I'll say it again, I want you to be successful and get through the program, my hope is you narrow it for your own benefit, and for the benefit of others—others are represented by lawyers—listen you got to let the lawyers—I know I am getting a shake of the head cuz you're not happy with prior representation, or I—putting words in your mouth with that, but I know in your case you were—but they are represented, and you got to let the lawyers do the work that they're doing for them, and not be involved in their cases. Katrina?

Katrina Thornton: Um yes your honor, congratulations on your express, Tony, um I think a round of applause and a spin of the wheel is warranted and then there is something I would like to briefly put on the record regarding the state's program expectations.

Judge Mchale: Okay, alright, Tony, anything else to add?

Anthony Jones: Um ya, you know, I don't know, its kind of a hard thing to articulate in this kind of setting, but, I respect you a lot, Judge Mchale. I think you're a good man.

Judge McHale: Thank you.

Anthony Jones: I see the weight that you give these issues and the care you bring to the program. It's rare. It's rare in the judiciary. Sadly so.

Judge Machale: Thank you, thank you very much. I mean I, I—I really do care about the program, as I look down at Christina as the head of the program, and the individuals that are in it, I do. But lets, lets I guess move on, I want to go ahead as we normally do with somebody being an express, we give you a round of applause and you get to spin the wheel, congratulations.

(General applause and wheel spin noise)

Judge Mchale: What is it?

Anthony Jones: Community Service Credit.

Judge Mchale: You don't need, does he not need them?

Anthony Jones: Um I'm almost done, I could use them. That will put me at like twenty hours.

Judge Mchale: Ok, ok. That's good. That's—and then y'all get the order?

Katrina Thornton: Yep. We have Tony next court date May 6th, 2025. 1:30pm here in person. Here in phase 3, here in full compliance, he spun the wheel he got one community service hour credit. Just need your signature. He is representing himself.

Anthony Jones: And, um, do I have to say my sober date for the record?

Katrina Thornton: Yes.

Anthony Jones: Ok. You want me to say it?

Katrina Thornton: Yes. If you're in agreement with the form of what we're...yep. And then you'll get a copy of this, I'm just gonna hand it to Judge Mchale for a signature.

Judge Mchale: I did not ask to start out with what your sober birthday was, that's my usual go to, we got into other—so, what is it?

Anthony Jones: So that was something I did want to address, just for myself in my own case. And um, can I clarify if sober birthdates are the point at which sanctions attach in these hearings?

Judge Mchale: Sober birthdate I, I uh—it is the day after your last use, um, um, I have to look back at when we had the sanctions as to, I think it was going back to the date of the UA, but I would have to look at that. Maybe someone else can

Katrina Thornton: January 3rd, 2025 is the sober birthdate for the purposes of drug court.

Judge Mchale: Ok. So that's what it was from then.

Anthony Jones: Oh no, I was asking if that's the, the, the, speaking of the sober birthday on the record, is that point at which a sanction attaches, as a breach of contract.

Judge Mchale: um, no its not, i mean, it's kind of different, because somebody can have a, um, hard to take that, cuz somebody can take what their sober birthdate is, um, even when they're in phase 1, and it's not something that, uh, I guess I don't understand your question.

Anthony Jones: um, does the state use the sober birthdate on record as an admission of a breach of contract to the opt in waiver and agreement. I'm trying to understand where the sanctions attach after a UA. Because its its, we spoke about it briefly once before and its my understanding that the UA sanctions represents a breach of contract. **Because its a diverted its a diverted its not a criminal issue, its a contract issue right?**

Judge Mchale: **No, its its, you're still, its an agreement. Its a waiver and agreement you signed. But we're still, its a criminal proceeding. So its not a contract proceeding,** so i think with with, uh with the sober birthdate um, ordinarily, a sober birthdate if there is a sanction goes back to the date of that hearing. There have been certain times when i because lets say there was a delay in a UA result being processed I have gone further back with the sober birthday for purposes of uh the sanction than just the courtroom that particular day. So I , as I recall, like I gave you the benefit of the doubt going back to when the UA was rather than the court hearing and so the consequence of that or the sanction as to compliance clock time would have gone back to that day, the day of the UA. So hopefully that, does that clear it up?

Anthony Jones: It does. A little bit. And so, um, I guess I'm trying to understand the, uh, the sanction though is a breach of contract. Is what it is. What's the governing authority of that sanction?

Katrina Thornton: And your honor I think we're getting kinda, too in the weeds to the point where he might be inquiring for legal advice for the court.

Judge Mchale: Yeah, I'm ah um. I'll just say it. **If you look at paragraph 13 of the waiver and agreement, that's where it says that one is subject to urinalysis and so one can be subject to an imposition of a sanction, um, with a urinalysis test.** It doesn't um, so, its its what I did and its what it's not its not a co-its a um, I think you're you're seeing two different things as far as contract law and, um, criminal law. So that, I mean, for your sanction that's what it went back to is the date of the UA. So that's where it went into place. And that's **because of a violation of the terms of the waiver and agreement, which requires you to be subject to random urinalysis.**

Anthony Jones: And um, to uh, to answer the prosecution's concern, I am clarifying so that I can state the correct date on the record without perjuring myself. Um, would the court agree or clarify whether that opt in waiver is an adhesion contract?

Judge McHale: I did not, um, its not, it is, I do not see it as an adhesion contract. Um, ya its not

Anthony Jones: It's not an adhesion contract? From what, So can the court clarify the governing authority for the sanction?

Judge Mchale: Ya know, we're dealing with just this hearing today, if you have other issues that you want to address, then you would need to note them and we can address them that way, but thats um you know, you agreed to come in to the program to to benefit from the program, and um, per paragraph 13 you had a positive UA, as a result there was a a non-incarceration sanction that was recommended and mean and thats, thats what it was.

Anthony Jones: I just want to make sure that I'm not being sanctioned by something that's not prohibited by drug court policy. Can the court clarify where in the contract I signed where in the contract I signed it says xylazine is prohibited?

Judge Mchale: Now, I'm not, I'm not, we talked about if you want to bring a hearing to address those other issues, we can do that, but um, you're, you looked through the handbook, you looked through the participation manual, um, I mean I think one would be hard to say that xylazine which is a tranquilizer is not uh uh mood impacting or enhancing substance in some way. So it ah, ah, that's what the sanction was for. That's it. So back, what do you see as your sober birthdate?

Anthony Jones: Well that's what I am trying to determine, I think that in the wording of the policy for prohibited substances that I agreed not to use, probably mood altering substances is the only term that could be used to describe where that's prohibited, but throughout the entire policy and procedure manual the term mood altering substance is not defined, and i feel like caffeine and nicotine are both mood altering substances, and so i think that in adhesion contract law ambiguity construes against the drafter. I think that the policy wording is overly vague.

Judge Mchale: You're you're you're. Let me just say, you're getting into the issues that I think you have addressed in your motion, so that's something that we're not gonna address today. So and I can, um, what I would do for today is just leave the sober birth dates as they were from last time which you say is your admitted sober birthdate, and then um your last use and then your sober birthdate from I forget the date again uh 1/3. But if there are other issues you want to address from the motion then that's something we need to address at another time.

Anthony Jones: So then to the best of my ability to state the truth my sober birthdate is 6/26/24.

Judge Mchale: Ok. Um, but you, so thats your sober birthdate, but you acknowledge that there was a sanction for a positive UA with xylazine on that other date.

Anthony Jones: I acknowledge that I received sanctions, but I don't acknowledge that I broke any of the contract terms that I agreed to when I opted in. I think those are wrongful sanctions for a non-prohibited substance.

Judge Mchale: Ok, um, well we can address this in another, ah, hearing for now, but I'm I'm still finding that the sober birthdate goes back to the time before finding that there was a positive uh xylazine UA from—the date keeps escaping me and I know I've got the order here but, somebody gonna help me with the date again you just had it.

Katrina Thornton: January 3rd.

Judge Mchale: I'm sorry, what was that?

Katrina Thornton: The sober for drug court purposes was January 3rd your honor.

Judge Mchale: Yeah, that's what I'll, I'll find for now. So for today, uh next hearing is set for May 6th at 1:30 that would be in person that will be here, there is one community service hour that was given, ah was an express, still in phase 3, working towards phase 4. Alright, oh did you want to put something on record?

Katrina Thornton: Yes your honor, at this time the state is putting Tony on notice that the continued filing of frivolous motions based on factually inaccurate representations and misinformation may result in the state ultimately seeking termination from the drug court program on the basis that he would be in violation of the drug court handbook rules, specifically the provision that um, prohibits disruptive behavior of any kind in drug court, at treatment, or in the community at large. I am filing a number of emails that tony has sent, um, sent a number of the team members, but specifically that I have seen from the prosecutors emails that began on I think on March 5th continuing up to as recently as this afternoon. I'm also providing Tony a copy of the emails that I am filing with the court now so I'll just ask that he acknowledge receipt of these emails that I'm handing over to him.

Judge Mchale: yeah those can be filed.

Katrina Thornton: And your honor I just need to make a further record just to make the state's expectation clear, I wanted to cite to page 15 of our drug court handbook, it prevents threatening, harassing, assaultive, disrespectful or disruptive behavior of any kind. And the filings that have been referenced today the motions, as well as the emails I just filed with the court and given to tony, ah, he has made a number of allegations regarding our drug court program that were kind of alluded to throughout this hearing and our discussions today. Specifically that allegations that drug testing is unreliable, that our drug court participants are denied their right to contest toxicology results, that the program engages in inconsistent sanctioning practices that result in unfair and unavoidable punishments. Tony's behavior has at this point become disruptive to the program and the treatment milieu at large. As discussed again his emails referenced other participant's cases explicitly. And it's disruptive by hyper

focusing other participants on inaccuracies that are not grounded in facts or science. I have concerns that he may be engaging in the unauthorized practice of law by giving other participants legal advice regarding their cases and their rights. He claims that drug court is violating the principles of fairness due process and ethical court proceedings. So today the state does want to put him on notice that continued disruptive behavior may result with the state requesting termination from this program. His continued participation in drug court may not continue to be sustainable as he is making his own success implausible, and is harming the program by giving misinformed and factually inaccurate information. State has concerns that the program may ultimately be unable to serve him in accordance with best practices if his behavior continues to disrupt the program. Similarly I have concerns that his needs may exceed the resources that drug court can provide him. Page 16 of our handbook references termination and says that there may be instances when your continuation in the drug court program is unproductive for you, for the program, or both. The court ultimately retains the decision regarding whether to terminate a participant from drug court, but in assessing whether continuation in the drug court program is productive for either you or the program, one of the factors the court will consider is whether there has been a failure to abide by the terms of the drug court agreement or rules of the handbook. Again acknowledging he did celebrate an express today, he is in compliance right, but i just want to make a really solid record and make it clear to everybody that the state has expectations that he abide each and every term in the handbook and the waiver and agreement that he signed, um, which is agreeing to those specific terms prohibiting behavior such as disruptive behavior.

Judge Mchale: Ok, um so i have signed the order next hearing as I said is May 6th next hearing is right here at 1:30pm in person.

Exhibit 2

ADULT DRUG COURT PLANNING INITIATIVE A GUIDE TO CREATING A PARTICIPANT HANDBOOK

The purpose of a participant handbook is to provide consumers with a clear understanding of the requirements and expectations of the program. The information contained in the handbook should be organized and easy to understand. It is recommended that the handbook be written at a seventh grade reading level so that the material can be comprehended by participants of varying educational degrees. To ensure reading comprehension levels, Flesch-Kincaid scores should be used and can be determined in Microsoft Word under “readability statistics.” In addition, the document should be visually appealing; paying close attention to spacing and the availability of white space on each page. The handbook should be written and designed in a manner so that clients will fully understand the operations of the program without feeling overwhelmed with material.

The participant handbook should have a cover that identifies the name of the program and the date of its last update. The first page of the manual should be the table of contents followed by a welcome letter written by whoever is responsible for the administration of the program. The remainder of the manual should consist of the following content:

The Adult Drug Court Team

It is important that participants know who is associated with your drug court and will most likely be working with them throughout the course of program. The members of your core drug court team should be clearly identified in the handbook by name and title. In addition, a telephone number for each member should be provided.

Mission Statement

The mission statement lets your consumers know the intended purpose of the program. By providing this information, participants will have a clear understanding of why the program exists.

Eligibility Requirements

A brief description of the criteria participant’s must meet in order to be considered eligible for the program should be provided. Information should include things such as criminal class, residency requirements and clinical criteria.

Program Requirements

Participants should be provided a clear understanding as to what is required of them while taking part in the drug court program. The minimum and maximum time spent in the program should be identified. In addition, general reporting requirements, employment expectations, frequency of treatment and court appearances should be listed.

Attendance and Absence Policy

The drug court's attendance and absentee policy should be clearly stated. Participants should be advised of the importance of timely arrival and the program's point of contact in the event of a necessary absence.

Court Sessions

The date, time and location of drug court sessions should be clearly identified in the handbook.

Drug Testing Protocol

The program's drug testing policy should be clearly stated. The expected method and frequency of testing and location of sample collection sites should be included. The process of identifying how to find out if a random sample deposit is required on any given day should be described.

Supervision Protocol

The type of supervision utilized by the drug court should be identified. Participants should be given a clear understanding as to the organization responsible for supervision and the frequency of reporting. The address and telephone number of supervising entity should be provided.

Prescription Medication Policy

The drug court's policy on prescription medication should be included in the handbook. Participants should be advised of whom to contact in the event they are prescribed medication while in the program. In addition, the type of acceptable documentation for prescription medication should be identified.

Incentives and Sanctions

The purpose of imposing sanctions and incentives should be explained. Furthermore, a short list of potential rewards and punishments should be included to give participants an idea of what to expect.

Fees

The drug court's fee policy should be explained. The reason for the cost, frequency of payment and the location of the cashier should be identified.

Transportation

The program's transportation policy should be explained. Resources as to where to seek transportation assistance services should be noted.

Graduation

Guidelines on how to successfully exit the program should be provided. Information pertaining to treatment, criminal record and clean time requirements should be clearly stated.

Termination

The program's policy and terms for unsuccessful discharge from the drug court should be provided.

General Rules

The basic rules and guidelines of the program should be clearly defined. Participants should be advised of the program's policy on matters such as drug/alcohol use, enabling, acceptable behaviors, dress code, pairing off and electronic device usage.

Infection Control Policy

It is recommended that participant's be advised of the drug court's policy on infectious disease control. It should be explained that program staff exercise universal precautions and are obligated to report instances of infectious disease that pose a threat to the general public to the local health department.

Program Phases

The drug court phase system of the program should be clearly identified. Clients should be made aware of the average duration of each phase and the milestones that must be met to advance to the next stage of the program.

Treatment

The treatment levels of care and type of treatment model utilized by the program should be identified and explained. Information pertaining to the frequency of care, days and time of service delivery and location of the treatment provider should be clearly indicated.

Releases of Information & Confidentiality

The program's policy on participant confidentiality and the need for releases of information should be clearly explained. Participants should be assured that their information is protected and will only be utilized for the intended purpose of the drug court program.

Complaints and Grievances

The program's procedures for filing complaints and grievances should be included. Participants should be made aware of their right to express opinions, recommendations and grievances in addition to their right to request and receive responses via a procedure of due process. The process for filing a complaint without fear of negative repercussions should be explained. Furthermore, the waiting period for an initial response to the grievance should be noted.

Frequently Asked Questions

It is recommended that a frequently asked questions section be included at the end of the handbook. This section should be compiled of questions that are most often posed to veteran treatment court staff and team members.

Contractual Agreement

The final page of the handbook should be the participant contractual agreement. This one-page document serves as a checklist of all requirements discussed in the handbook. It should also contain a check-box indicating that the client has received a copy of the participant handbook and understands the requirements and expectations of the program. The participant should sign the contractual agreement and the program coordinator should also sign as a witness to the participant's signature. The participant should be provided a photocopy of the contract and the original should be stored in the participant's file.

Updates to Participant Manual

The participant handbook should be updated immediately following any changes in the program's policies and procedures. Contact information for drug court team members should be updated any time there is a change in program staff or team members. In addition, the handbook should be reviewed annually to identify and address any needed programmatic adjustments.